

Supplementary Information for the manuscript:

Exceptions to the temperature-size rule: no Lilliput Effect in end-Permian ostracods (Crustacea) from Aras Valley (NW Iran)

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Supplementary Information in external files:

Data D1: Naetscher_et_al_2023_D1_Ostracoda.csv (Ostracod occurrence dataset)

Data D2: Naetscher_et_al_2023_D2_Temperature.csv (Temperature dataset from Gliwa et al. 2022)

Data D3: Naetscher_et_al_2023_D3_Rego.csv (Rego-Approach results)

+ R Code and RData file

Figure S1: Instar classification plots (length x height) of the most parsimonious gaussian mixture model (VEI in both cases) from the R package mclust (left side), and BIC plots of all tested models (right side) of A) *B. ottomanensis* (adults and five juvenile instars) and B) *F. obunca* (adults and four juvenile instars)

A) *Bairdiacypris ottomanensis*

B) *Fabalicypis obunca*

Table S1: Tables visualising the methodology of the Rego Approach (Rego et al., 2012): A) Full ostracod assemblage sizes (mm²) for each zone (all taxa) and body size of boundary crossing taxa (BC) in the earlier zone (BC pre) and the later zone (BC post); B) shows the calculations from the Rego approach to determine the contributions of within-taxon size changes and size selective (dis-)appearances to the overall size change; C) Results from the Rego approach calculations for absolute body size changes as can be seen in the main manuscript in Fig. 2

A					
zone1	all taxa	BC pre	zone2	all taxa	BC post
1	-2.055638	-2.211746	2	-1.954303	-1.990634
2	-1.954303	-1.950043	3	-2.321679	-2.321679
3	-2.321679	-2.334448	4	-2.353702	-2.355173
4	-2.353702	0	5	-1.811332	0
5	-1.811332	-1.875782	6	-1.548347	-1.580837
6	-1.548347	-1.548347	7	-1.765117	-1.771887
7	-1.765117	-1.876080	8	-2.284362	-2.284362
8	-2.284362	-2.290076	9	-2.309771	-2.304415
B	Assemblage size shift	Disappearance effect	Within-lineage effect	Appearance effect	
1 2	all taxa2 - all taxa1	BC pre1 - all taxa1	BC post2 - BC pre1	all taxa2 - BC post2	
2 3	all taxa3 - all taxa2	BC pre2 - all taxa2	BC post3 - BC pre2	all taxa3 - BC post3	
3 4	all taxa4 - all taxa3	BC pre3 - all taxa3	BC post4 - BC pre3	all taxa4 - BC post4	
4 5	all taxa5 - all taxa4	BC pre4 - all taxa4	BC post5 - BC pre4	all taxa5 - BC post5	
5 6	all taxa6 - all taxa5	BC pre5 - all taxa5	BC post6 - BC pre5	all taxa6 - BC post6	
6 7	all taxa7 - all taxa6	BC pre6 - all taxa6	BC post7 - BC pre6	all taxa7 - BC post7	
7 8	all taxa8 - all taxa7	BC pre7 - all taxa7	BC post8 - BC pre7	all taxa8 - BC post8	
8 9	all taxa9 - all taxa8	BC pre8 - all taxa8	BC post9 - BC pre8	all taxa9 - BC post9	
C	Assemblage size shift	Disappearance effect	Within-lineage effect	Appearance effect	
1 2	0.101335	-0.156108	0.221112	0.036331	
2 3	-0.367376	0.00426	-0.371636	0	
3 4	-0.032023	-0.012769	-0.020725	0.00147100	
4 5	0.54237	2.353702	0	-1.811332	
5 6	0.262985	-0.06445	0.294945	0.03249	
6 7	-0.21677	0	-0.22354	0.00677	
7 8	-0.519245	-0.110963	-0.408282	0	
8 9	-0.025409	-0.005714	-0.014339	-0.005356	

Figure S2: Sedimentary profile of the Aras Valley section (NW Iran) on the left, with a red horizontal line indicating the extinction horizon (EH) and a green line at the Permian-Triassic boundary. A) shows the loess-smoothed mean calculated temperature derived from oxygen isotope measurements of the ostracod carapaces with the red shading representing the loess-smoothed SD; red stars show the original data from Gliwa et al. (2022), grey dots are the interpolated data used in this study. B) is the $\delta^{13}C$ curve that was reverse-engineered from Gliwa et al. 2022, C) is the corrected-in-bin diversity (Alroy et al. 2008) D) to H) show loess-smoothed median body size curves with the shaded area representing loess-smoothed MAD and grey points representing the raw body size data of the D) full assemblage, E) order Podocopida, F) order Platycopida, G) genus *Fabalicyparis*, and H) species body size of *B. ottomanensis* (blue at the top) and *F. obunca* (green at the bottom). The dashed lines in D), E), G) and H) represent loess-smoothed body size curves of the median valve size of the A-1 instars.

Figure S3: Correlation plot of the three variables intended for use in the general least square (gls) models ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, temperature, corrected in-bin-diversity). According to Dormann et al. (2007), we excluded $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from the variables, as the negative correlation between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and the temperature values is too high (-0.75)

Table S2: AIC selection process of the autoregressive (p) and the moving average (q) variables for the generalised least squares (gls) models to correct for temporal autocorrelation. Models with only an autoregressive variable between 0 and 5 were tested, followed by the same procedure for the moving average variable. The best p and q (lowest AIC & BIC) were used for the environmental proxy models in Table S3.

Whole assemblage						Assemblage instar A-1					
p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC	p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC
0	4	2249.393	0	4	2249.393	0	4	104.135	0	4	104.135
1	5	1854.625	1	5	1988.245	1	5	-74.777	1	5	-21.048
2	6	1810.915	2	6	1905.988	2	6	-69.312	2	6	-41.783
3	7	1803.587	3	7	1861.675	3	7	-65.301	3	7	-52.783
4	8	1806.76	4	8	1856.372	4	8	-59.940	4	8	-52.689
5	9	1803.098	5	9	1851.025	5	9	-54.227	5	9	-52.584
F. obunca						F. obunca instar A-1					
p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC	p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC
0	4	409.0195	0	4	409.0195	0	4	-122.786	0	4	-122.786
1	5	399.1037	1	5	399.714	1	5	-126.856	1	5	-126.922
2	6	404.8504	2	6	405.1348	2	6	-122.7	2	6	-122.827
3	7	410.1196	3	7	409.7242	3	7	-119.22	3	7	-118.665
4	8	415.4915	4	8	415.3809	4	8	-120.596	4	8	-116.906
5	9	421.226	5	9	421.0906	5	9	-117.601	5	9	-115.152
B. ottomanensis						B. ottomanensis instar A-1					
p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC	p (AR)	d.f.	BIC	q (MA)	d.f.	BIC
0	4	552.9133	0	4	552.9133	0	4	-125.085	0	4	-125.085
1	5	455.7691	1	5	490.6759	1	5	-123.008	1	5	-122.229
2	6	447.8311	2	6	473.28	2	6	-122.547	2	6	-121.339
3	7	451.2706	3	7	460.04	3	7	-118.33	3	7	-117.48
4	8	457.1373	4	8	462.9549	4	8	-118.24	4	8	-121.043
5	9	462.5875	5	9	468.2628	5	9	-115.199	5	9	-117.396

Table S3: Model results of the gls (generalised least squares) models , correcting for temporal autocorrelation, for the full assemblage, *F. obunca* and *B. ottomanensis*, as well as a subset of only the A-1 instar grouping for each of these, testing the influence of temperature and diversity on body size

		Value	SE	t	p	Resid. SE	d.f.	d.f. resid.	AIC	BIC
full assemblage (p=5, q=5)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	-1.907	0.056	-34.275	0	0.607	1624	1623	2127.618	2192.322
~ T	(Intercept)	-2.030	0.148	-13.704	0	0.6027	1624	1622	2138.202	2208.29
	temperature	0.003	0.004	0.885	0.376					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-2.111	0.113	-18.61	0	0.554	1366	1364	1743.964	1811.8
	diversity	0.043	0.022	1.975	0.048					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-2.246	0.173	-13.012	0	0.551	1366	1363	1754.188	1827.232
	diversity	0.04	0.022	1.85	0.065					
	temperature	0.004	0.004	0.9465	0.344					
full assemblage instar A-1 (p=2, q=3)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	-1.621	0.048	-33.549	0	0.233	371	370	-29.734	-2.339
~ T	(Intercept)	-1.891	0.129	-14.628	0	0.328	371	369	-13.627	17.659
	temperature	0.008	0.003	2.331	0.020					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-1.909	0.080	-23.742	0	0.276	335	333	-101.145	-74.488
	diversity	0.072	0.017	4.325	0					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-2.030	0.130	-15.583	0	0.272	335	332	-88.688	-54.442
	diversity	0.069	0.017	4.188	0					
	temperature	0.004	0.004	1.127	0.260					
F. obunca full species (p=1, q=1)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	2.3368	0.031	-74.4225	0	0.423	388	387	414.178	430.011
~ T	(Intercept)	-2.016	0.187	-10.7588	0	0.421	388	386	421.654	441.433
	temperature	-0.011	0.006	-1.7327	0.084					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-2.5189	0.204	-12.3679	0	0.435	320	318	374.416	393.226
	diversity	0.058	0.058	1.011	0.313					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-2.069	0.39	-5.311	0	0.433	320	317	382.291	404.844
	diversity	0.031	0.06	0.518	0.605					
	temperature	-0.012	0.009	-1.349	0.178					
F. obunca instar A-1 (p=1, q=1)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	-1.962	37.885	-0.052	0.959	37.885	91	91	-179.482	-169.482
~ T	(Intercept)	-2.083	0.077	-26.98	0	0.0965	91	89	-165.712	-155.757
	temperature	0.005	0.003	1.868	0.065					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-2.098	0.082	-25.65	0	0.087	78	76	-148.54	-136.886
	diversity	0.047	0.023	2.049	0.044					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-2.129	0.139	-15.339	0	0.088	78	75	-136.695	-122.79
	diversity	0.048	0.024	1.967	0.053					
	temperature	0.001	0.003	0.312	0.756					
B. ottomanensis full species (p=2, q=3)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	-1.891	0.079	-23.8107	0	0.509	357	356	413.715	440.839
~ T	(Intercept)	-2.174	0.329	-6.608	0	0.508	357	355	422.776	453.752
	temperature	0.007	0.008	0.886	0.376					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-1.577	0.177	-8.91	0	0.508	357	355	416.975	447.952
	diversity	-0.064	0.031	-2.073	0.0389					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-1.835	0.372	-4.93	0	0.508	357	354	426.197	461.021
	diversity	-0.0626	0.031	-2.028	0.043					
	temperature	0.006	0.008	0.785	0.433					
B. ottomanensis instar A-1 (p=0, q=0)										
~ 1	(Intercept)	-1.4048	0.00978	-143.561	0	0.0886	82	81	-154.328	-149.54
~ T	(Intercept)	-1.5458	0.146	-10.5807	0	0.0886	82	80	-143.816	-136.67
	temperature	0.0034	0.0035	0.967	0.336					
~ Div	(Intercept)	-1.4316	0.0342	-41.804	0	0.08879	82	80	-144.868	-137.722
	diversity	0.0056	0.0068	0.818	0.4158					
~ Div +T	(Intercept)	-1.5915	0.1542	-10.318	0	0.08872	82	79	-134.563	-125.085
	diversity	0.0064	0.00688	0.93	0.355					
	temperature	0.00379	0.0035	1.0626	0.291					

Figure S4: Histograms of instar abundances within the 18 ostracod species ($n > 9$) for which we classified instar clusters with the Gaussian mixture modelling method in the R package mclust. Almost all of these species, except *Kempfina* sp. 1 and *P. pulchra*, show more or less well distributed sampling of the different instar groupings, indicating a low to moderate energy autochthonous thanatocoenosis with a lack of substantial post-mortem transport (Boomer et al. 2003)

Table S4: Model results from the paleo time series trend analyses (with the R package paleoTS) for the six instars of *B. ottomanensis*

<i>Bairdiacypris ottomanensis</i> up to 2.88 m					
A (Comparing 5 models [n = 4, method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	4.912249	3	Inf	Inf	0
URW	4.620334	2	6.759333	0	0.5
Stasis	4.620334	2	6.759333	0	0.5
covTrack d13C	4.721857	3	Inf	Inf	0
covTrack T	4.625023	3	Inf	Inf	0
A-1 (Comparing 5 models [n = 9, method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	10.669700	3	-10.539400	0.7996354	0.218
URW	8.620313	2	-11.240627	0.0984084	0.31
Stasis	8.669518	2	-11.339035	0.00	0.326
covTrack d13C	9.699622	3	-8.599244	2.7397915	0.083
covTrack T	9.433041	3	-8.066082	3.2729534	0.063
A-2 (Comparing 5 models [n = 10, method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	13.01558	3	-16.03116	3.843889	0.061
URW	12.79467	2	-19.87505	0	0.42
Stasis	12.79467	2	-19.87505	0	0.42
covTrack d13C	12.79550	3	-15.59099	4.284057	0.049
covTrack T	12.79504	3	-15.59008	4.284966	0.049
A-3 (Comparing 5 models [n = 9, method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	11.69596	3	-12.59191	4.740635e+00	0.041
URW	11.66627	2	-17.33255	0	0.436
Stasis	11.66627	2	-17.33255	3.090861e-13	0.436
covTrack d13C	11.69085	3	-12.58169	4.750856e+00	0.041
covTrack T	11.81685	3	-12.83370	4.498847e+00	0.046
A-4 (Comparing 5 models [n = 8 method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	8.986042	3	-5.972084	5.544519e+00	0.28
URW	8.958301	2	-11.516602	0	0.452
Stasis	8.958301	2	-11.516602	1.776357e-13	0.452
covTrack d13C	9.016397	3	-6.032794	5.483808e+00	0.029
covTrack T	9.304902	3	-6.609804	4.906798e+00	0.039
A-5 (Comparing 5 models [n = 4, method = Joint])					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	3.924250	3	Inf	Inf	0
URW	3.920286	2	8.159428	0	0.5
Stasis	3.920286	2	8.159428	0	0.5
covTrack d13C	3.945088	3	Inf	Inf	0
covTrack T	3.992983	3	Inf	Inf	0

Table S5: Model results from the paleo time series trend analyses (with the R package paleoTS) for the five instars of *F. obunca*

<i>Fabalicypis obunca</i>					
A					
Comparing 5 models [n = 6, method = Joint]					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	5.163663	3	7.672673	9.859453	0.004
URW	5.093390	2	-2.186780	0	0.495
Stasis	5.093390	2	-2.186780	0	0.495
covTrack d13C	5.174760	3	7.650480	9.837260	0.004
covTrack T	5.103075	3	7.793850	9.980630	0.003
A-1					
Comparing 5 models [n = 10, method = Joint]					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	11.86466	3	-13.72932	3.762617	0.064
URW	11.56513	2	-17.41597	0.075965	0.407
Stasis	11.60311	2	-17.49194	0	0.423
covTrack d13C	11.67564	3	-13.35128	4.140654	0.053
covTrack T	11.65322	3	-13.30644	4.185499	0.052
A-2					
Comparing 5 models [n = 11, method = Joint]					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	13.32414	3	-17.21971	3.882005	0.057

URW	13.30086	2	-21.10172	0	0.396
Stasis	13.30086	2	-21.10172	1.421085e-14	0.396
covTrack d13C	13.32165	3	-17.21472	3.887001	0.057
covTrack T	13.82214	3	-18.21570	2.886019	0.094
A-3					
Comparing 5 models [n = 11, method = Joint]					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	15.66575	3	-21.90293	3.917762	0.058
URW	15.66035	2	-25.82069	0	0.412
Stasis	15.66035	2	-25.82069	0	0.412
covTrack d13C	15.68043	3	-21.93229	3.888405	0.059
covTrack T	15.66564	3	-21.90270	3.917988	0.058
A-4					
Comparing 5 models [n = 9, method = Joint]					
	logL	K	AICc	dAICc	Akaike.wt
GRW	10.54391	3	-10.28782	4.782015	0.040
URW	10.53492	2	-15.06984	0	0.435
Stasis	10.53492	2	-15.06984	0	0.435
covTrack d13C	10.56756	3	-10.33511	4.734728	0.041
covTrack T	10.77423	3	-10.74846	4.321380	0.050

Figure S5: Boxplot of the body sizes of the species from the post-extinction assemblage, showing that six of them are larger than most of the other species in this assemblage (*Fabalicypris cf. minuta*, *Fabalicypris veronicae*, *Iranokirkbya brandneri*, *Kempfina qinglaili*, *Kempfina sp. 1*, *Kempfina sp. 2*), driving the significant increase in overall body size across the extinction horizon.

Table S6: Posthoc Tukey HSD of ANOVA results between body sizes of the twelve species from the post-extinction assemblage of podocopids from 0.01 m to 0.50 m showing that six of them are significantly larger than most of the other species in this assemblage (*Fabalitypris cf. minuta*, *Fabalitypris veronicae*, *Iranokirkbya brandneri*, *Kempfina qinglaili*, *Kempfina sp. 1*, *Kempfina sp. 2*), driving the significant increase in overall body size across the extinction horizon (d.f. = 11, Residuals = 351), only significant results with $p < 0.05$ are shown.

	diff	lwr	upr	p adj
<i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	-0.511	-0.993	-0.029	0.027
<i>Fabalitypris cf. minuta</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	0.466	0.100	0.833	0.002
<i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	0.534	0.169	0.900	0.000
<i>Kempfina qinglaili</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	0.644	0.264	1.024	0.000
<i>Kempfina sp. 1</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	0.615	0.207	1.024	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	-1.480	-2.176	-0.784	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	-1.257	-1.720	-0.793	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Bairdia hassi</i>	-0.598	-1.104	-0.091	0.007
<i>Kempfina qinglaili</i> - <i>Bairdia sp. 2</i>	0.836	0.067	1.604	0.020
<i>Kempfina sp. 1</i> - <i>Bairdia sp. 2</i>	0.807	0.025	1.590	0.036
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Bairdia sp. 2</i>	-1.288	-2.253	-0.324	0.001
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Bairdia sp. 2</i>	-1.065	-1.878	-0.252	0.001
<i>Fabalitypris cf. minuta</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	0.977	0.561	1.394	0.000
<i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	1.045	0.630	1.460	0.000
<i>Iranokirkbya brandneri</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	1.442	0.220	2.664	0.007
<i>Kempfina qinglaili</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	1.155	0.727	1.583	0.000
<i>Kempfina sp. 1</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	1.126	0.673	1.580	0.000
<i>Kempfina sp. 2</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	0.594	0.066	1.122	0.013
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	-0.969	-1.693	-0.246	0.001
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Carinaknightina hofmanni</i>	-0.746	-1.249	-0.242	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Fabalitypris cf. minuta</i>	-1.947	-2.599	-1.294	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Fabalitypris cf. minuta</i>	-1.723	-2.118	-1.329	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Fabalitypris cf. minuta</i>	-1.064	-1.508	-0.620	0.000
<i>Kempfina sp. 2</i> - <i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i>	-0.451	-0.875	-0.027	0.026
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i>	-2.014	-2.666	-1.363	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i>	-1.791	-2.184	-1.397	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Fabalitypris veronicae</i>	-1.132	-1.575	-0.689	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Iranokirkbya brandneri</i>	-2.411	-3.732	-1.090	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Iranokirkbya brandneri</i>	-2.188	-3.402	-0.973	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Iranokirkbya brandneri</i>	-1.529	-2.760	-0.297	0.003
<i>Kempfina sp. 2</i> - <i>Kempfina qinglaili</i>	-0.561	-0.997	-0.124	0.002
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Kempfina qinglaili</i>	-2.124	-2.784	-1.464	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina qinglaili</i>	-1.901	-2.308	-1.494	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina qinglaili</i>	-1.242	-1.697	-0.786	0.000
<i>Kempfina sp. 2</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 1</i>	-0.532	-0.993	-0.071	0.009
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 1</i>	-2.095	-2.772	-1.419	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 1</i>	-1.872	-2.305	-1.439	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 1</i>	-1.213	-1.692	-0.734	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 2</i>	-1.563	-2.292	-0.835	0.000
<i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 2</i>	-1.340	-1.851	-0.829	0.000
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Kempfina sp. 2</i>	-0.681	-1.231	-0.131	0.003
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Microcheilinella cf. perexilis</i>	0.882	0.143	1.622	0.006
<i>Reviya sp. 1</i> - <i>Microcheilinella sp. 1</i>	0.659	0.132	1.186	0.003